

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF PERSONALITY CHANGES IN OLD AGE

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Abstract. Moving away from active participation in production in old age, changing social position with retirement are important changes in the social situation of development. The article describes the characteristics of old age, changes in the emotional sphere of a person, problems that arise in this age, egocentrism of old age, and gender differences.

Key words: old age, emotional sphere, meaning of life, behavior, social environment, self-awareness, egocentrism.

СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ФАКТОРЫ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ В ПОЖИЛОМ ВОЗРАСТЕ

Аннотация. Отход от активного участия в производстве в пожилом возрасте, изменение социального положения с выходом на пенсию являются важными изменениями социальной ситуации развития. В статье описаны особенности пожилого возраста, изменения в эмоциональной сфере человека, проблемы, возникающие в этом возрасте, эгоцентризм старости, гендерные различия.

Ключевые слова: старость, эмоциональная сфера, смысл жизни, поведение, социальная среда, самосознание, эгоцентризм.

Aging is an important stage of human ontogenesis, without studying it it is impossible to build a holistic concept of mental development and form a positive image of aging. The psychology of old age is currently underdeveloped. Gerontopsychology was first mentioned in the West in 1922 by the American psychologist J. Hall and covered in the monograph "Old Age". In 1974, the Russian scientist M.D. Aleksandrova published the book "Social Psychological Gerontology" on gerontopsychology.

In the recent past, researchers considered old age to be only a period of decline. Old age is unique in the uniqueness of accumulated experience and the ability to share it with other generations. In old age, a person decides the following question: to preserve his old social ties, and to establish new social ties, or to join them in the interests of his loved ones, or to enter an individual life to solve his own problems. This choice determines one or another adaptation strategy - to preserve oneself as a person or as an individual. Depending on this choice, the strategy of adaptation, the leader's activity can be directed to save himself as a person, or to save him as an individual.

In the "closed circuit type" adaptation strategy, it is manifested in a decrease in the level of interests and aspirations to the outside world, egocentrism, weakening of emotional control, a complex of inaccuracy, irritability, sometimes indifference to others. This aging pattern is sometimes referred to as "passive aging" or loss of social interest. The change of personal structures is primarily affected by the cessation of active work. For many people, retirement is painful. Deprivation of a job that is the meaning of a person's life is a stressful situation. The destruction of the stereotype of the usual life, the change of social status, the sharp narrowing of the social circle often lead to depression, Consciousness, mobility are lost, intensively active people become passive.

There are changes in the emotional sphere. The processes of impoverishment of emotional life lead to the fact that people who have lived a stormy, emotionally intense life gradually become "calm", find joy in a narrow circle, sometimes their life becomes completely dark. An old man is stingy with words. The range of their feelings narrows, they focus their love on the family, even on one of its members (the only grandson or granddaughter), which becomes the center of all the joys of life for them.

The environment of an elderly person is changing: friends and peers are passing away, there is no energy and opportunity to start new ones. The range of interests narrows to questions about a person's health, desires and needs, and sometimes harms the interests of loved ones. Old age egocentrism and selfishness appear. Feeling the importance of one's own personality, focusing on diseases hides everything else. Characteristic features such as behavior and desire to teach are strengthened. Old age infirmity, indolence and softness appear. Elderly people are characterized by thrift, sometimes they become stingy. This is a hidden form of struggle for independence and freedom. Since elderly people, for various reasons, do not expect to earn money on their own for unexpected needs, the only way to maintain independence is to save every penny, food, things.

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Self-esteem elderly people are able to most accurately assess themselves and their capabilities, the ability to perform any activity, the ability to understand the nature of existing relationships with loved ones, etc. Elderly self-esteem declines with age. As the future shrinks, a person turns more and more to the past, to its analysis and evaluation. The past starts to excite a person more than the present. There is a summary of the results of life, a rethinking, a balanced reassessment of the past life. If life has brought satisfaction, then there will be a sense of the fullness and usefulness of one's existence, the ability to come to terms with the inevitable, the understanding that death is not terrible. On the contrary, the life lived is perceived as a series of mistakes and unfulfilled opportunities, there is regret about the impossibility of starting again, the lack of time for this increases the fear of death.

The rich experience of the past, its realization forms a special attitude of an elderly person to the present. Life wisdom, a unique philosophy of life emerges. Life satisfaction and self-esteem affect the level of social adaptation of an elderly person. Ambition, pride, vanity decrease with

age. With age, a person begins to look at the characteristics and events of life, as if it were an epic. But at the same time, although a little, sociality and humanity are reduced. In this regard, the opportunity to work among people decreases. People begin to tire of the old man.

In order to, self-awareness is realized in the construction of life perspectives - in the synthesis of a person's ideas about the past, present and future. It works as a mechanism for integrating the individual in various forms of manifestation in professional and social roles.

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